

Palliative Pearls (PP13) - formulary focused care - opioids for non-cancer pain (cellulitis)

Lymphedema is known to be a common precipitant for cellulitis where pain severity can become disproportionate. The formulary clearly lays emphasis on the role of good analgesia including use of opioids in the management of pain related with cellulitis.

In addition to the careful use of opioids, following measures are advised: Bed rest and elevation of the affected limbs on pillows. Regular analgesia, P.R.N. Paracetamol being the first line agent with NSAIDs as the alternative.

Practical difficulties with the practice of elevation might prevent it from being applied.

The fact that Opioid prescription might be necessary to control the pain, lays down the foundation for discussing the pros and cons of using opioids on a symptomatic basis in non-cancer pain.

This contrasts with the practice of first determining its applicability to the setting, based upon diagnosis (cancer pain only). Using this indication as the entry point for use of opioids in non-cancer pain poses a specific challenge, and asks whether a discussion about prognosis ought to be made a central tenet to every decision to use opioids for pain control in the cancer patient.

Other indications where opioid use has been advised in the non-cancer pain setting include neuropathic pain (where opioids such as tramadol, tapentadol and low-dose morphine are considered third line options), procedural pain, wound pain and musculoskeletal pain. It might be important to note that use in all these indications carries a different, albeit real risk for dependence.

There might be a need to decide upon a reasonable duration of time which is to be considered long enough for the phenomena of physical dependence, tolerance, opioid-induced hyperalgesia and potentially significant endocrinological effects to become significant enough to impact the patient's quality of life. Is the expected survival to be 6 months, 12 months or longer? An advanced cancer diagnosis might not lend itself automatically to a low threshold for opioid prescription. And what about the functional status, can it be considered ephemeral to this discussion?

References

Wilcock, A., Howard, P., Toller, C. S., Droney, J., & Charlesworth, S. (Eds.). (2025). *Palliative care formulary* (9th ed.). Pharmaceutical Press.